

Physical aging of toughened epoxy polymers

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Introduction

Toughened epoxy polymers have found widespread application in adhesives and composites. This is in large part thanks to the work of groups led by Kinloch and Pearson, e.g. [1-4]. Orders of magnitude improvements in fracture energy, G , have been reported with the addition of just a few percent of rubber. The rubber can be added as preformed particles, known as core-shell rubber particles [5] or as an adduct which phase separates out during the curing process [6].

Recently, we were the first to report on the effect of the rate of cure and the subsequent rapid gelation and solidification of the matrix can have on the ‘toughenability’ of the epoxy matrix [7]. We reported a significant reduction in the toughness enhancement when the epoxy polymers are cured at high rates. Furthermore, the reduction in toughness was found to be ubiquitous and occurred whether the rubber particles were pre-formed or formed via reaction induced phase separation. Incerti *et al.* [7] demonstrated the importance of considering the choice of manufacturing process when designing using nano-toughened polymers. An increased rate of cure, will lead to a lower on-mould time. This is preferential from a commercial standpoint, but can be detrimental to the final material properties of the adhesive or composite.

A second issue that has not been much reported in the literature is the evolution of toughness over time. For instance, if an aerospace structural component is manufactured using a toughened epoxy resin, how sure can we be that the fracture toughness measured at the start of the component’s life is the same value as the aircraft approaches retirement. Or, how does aging of polymers affect the toughness of rubber-modified epoxy polymers.

Kropka and co-workers at Sandia National Laboratories [8] have led the way on the topic of aging of epoxy resins. They have focused on measuring the increase in yield stress in compression and the attendant reduction in volume of the resin. Inspired by this work, the current study investigates the effect of physical aging on the toughness of epoxy polymers toughened with preformed core-shell rubber particles. The results to date demonstrate that a significant reduction in measured fracture energy is observed, while the increase in yield strength demonstrated by Kropka *et al.* is also reproduced for our polymer formulation. A possible mechanistic explanation for the observed behaviour is proposed and discussed. This may assist design engineers to specify the resin formulations accordingly, taking into account the estimated material toughness at the end of the

designed life as well as the toughness of the material as-manufactured.

Experimental

Materials

An model amine-cured epoxy system was used in the current work. The resin was a standard diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 185 g/eq, ‘Araldite LY556’ from Huntsman, UK. This was cured with a stoichiometric amount of a polyether-amine, ‘Jeffamine D-230’ from Huntsman, UK. Core-shell rubber (CSR) particles were obtained pre-dispersed at 40 wt% in DGEBA, ‘Albidur EP2240A’ (Evonik Hanse, Germany).

Epoxy polymer formulations containing 3%, 6% and 9% by weight of CSR nanoparticles were prepared and cast in picture frame aluminium moulds to create plaques of material. The stoichiometric ratios of resin and hardener were adjusted to account for the presence of the rubber nanoparticles. The polymers were cured isothermally at 60° C for two hours, with an additional post-curing step at 90° C for an additional two hours. This was followed by a slow in-oven cooling at approximately 1° C/min in order to mitigate the influence of thermally induced residual stresses.

Thermal analysis and aging procedure

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the bulk samples were measured via dynamic mechanical analysis in three-point bending mode at 1 Hz and at a ramp rate of 1° C/min. The T_g was determined as the global peak of the $\tan \delta$ curve. A Discovery Hybrid-Rheometer (TA Instruments, UK) was used in axial mode to measure T_g .

Following the manufacture of the plaques, they were vacuum sealed in a polyamide bag and placed in a temperature controlled chamber to accelerate physical aging. The temperature of the chamber was set to 5°C below the glass transition temperature of the control sample as manufactured. The samples were then extracted after 0 (as-manufactured), 9, 17, 31, 57, 126, 196 and 365 days. Test samples were machined from the aged plaques as appropriate.

Mechanical Testing

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed to obtain the tensile Young’s modulus, E_t , and tensile yield stress, $\sigma_{y,ut}$. Uniaxial compression tests were performed to determine the uniaxial compressive yield stress, $\sigma_{y,uc}$.

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) tests were performed to obtain the fracture energy, G_{Ic} , in the opening mode according to the ASTM standard. The fracture energy

was computed using the energy method. A razor blade cooled to -90°C was tapped into the notch prior to testing to ensure the presence of a sharp crack.

Results and Discussion

The glass transition temperature of the unmodified and unaged polymer was measured as 85°C . Thus, the samples were aged isothermally at 80°C . This elevated temperature accelerates the physical aging process, but is not a sufficiently high temperature to promote any annealing or recovery of the material.

Typical stress strain curves for the unmodified epoxy polymer as a function of aging time in days are given in Figure 1 (a), while typical stress-strain curves for a polymer containing 9 wt.% of CSR nanoparticles are given in Figure 1 (b). It can be clearly observed that aging results in an increase in the measured yield-stress. A slight increase in tensile modulus can also be detected. Furthermore, the addition of the CSR nanoparticles results in a reduction in both the yield strength and tensile modulus.

Figure 1: Typical stress-strain curves of (a) aged unmodified epoxy polymer and (b) aged epoxy polymers modified with 9 wt.% of CSR nanoparticles.

Uniaxial compression tests were also conducted to obtain the yield stress in compression. The measured yield stress in uniaxial tension, $\sigma_{y,ut}$, and uniaxial compression, $\sigma_{y,uc}$, from the unmodified epoxy polymers is given in Figure 2. Yielding of polymers is often sensitive to hydrostatic stress. It can be seen in Figure 2 that for an unaged sample the yield stress in uniaxial compression is greater than that in uniaxial tension. However, after six months of aging, the yield values are almost identical. This indicates a loss of pressure sensitivity due to aging. Sultan and McGarry and later others [9-12] demonstrated that this yield behaviour could be well approximated by a modified von Mises criterion of the following form:

$$\tau_{vm} = \tau_y - \mu_{vm}\sigma_{hyd} \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_{vm} = \sigma_{vm}/\sqrt{3}$ is the shear yield stress under the conditions of pure shear and μ_{vm} is the pressure sensitivity coefficient. In a state of uniaxial tension along the 1-direction the von Mises equivalent stress is equal to σ_1 , while the hydrostatic stress, σ_{vm} , is given as $\sigma_1/3$, where $\sigma_1 > 0$. In a uniaxial compression state, the hydrostatic component remains the same as for uniaxial tension, while σ_{vm} is given as $-\sigma_1$ where $\sigma_1 < 0$.

Figure 2: Measured yield stress in uniaxial tension and uniaxial compression as a function of aging time.

The measured fracture energy as a function of aging time is given in Figure 3. It can be seen that adding any amount of CSR nanoparticles results in an order of magnitude improvement in fracture energy. Such behaviour has been reported previously and is not particularly illuminating in the context of the current paper [13]. However, it can be seen that as the sample ages, particularly after 40 days of aging that a reduction in the measured fracture energy is recorded. For example, for an epoxy polymer modified with 9 wt.% of CSR particles the fracture energy drops from a value $2,584 \pm 165 \text{ J/m}^2$ for the as manufactured sample to a value of $2,271 \pm 79 \text{ J/m}^2$. Interestingly, a greater reduction in measured fracture energy is recorded for an epoxy polymer modified with 3 wt.% of CSR particles, from $2,728 \pm 215 \text{ J/m}^2$ to $1,320 \pm 81 \text{ J/m}^2$ after 196 days of aging, which is a reduction of over 50% from the as-manufactured value.

Figure 3: Measured fracture energy of unmodified epoxy polymers and polymers modified with 3, 6 and 9 wt.% of CSR nanoparticles.

Huang and Kinloch have provided a model [11,12], which is widely used to predict the toughness of rubber toughened polymers. The model states that the fracture energy of a toughened polymer, G_c , can be expressed as the sum of the fracture energy of the un-modified polymer, G_{cu} , plus the toughening contribution from the rubber particles, ψ . The toughening mechanisms can be mainly identified as localized shear banding and plastic void growth initiated by cavitation of the rubber particles. The energy contribution for localized shear-band yielding is given by:

$$\Delta G_s = 0.5V_p\sigma_y\gamma_f F'(r_y) \quad (2)$$

where V_p is the volume fraction of particles, σ_y is the compressive yield stress of the matrix, γ_f is the fracture strain of the polymer without particle addition and $F'(r_y)$ is a polynomial fitting function that depends on the particle radius, r_p , V_p , and r_y . The value of r_y can be calculated via:

$$r_y = K_{vm}^2 \left(1 + \frac{\mu_m}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 r_{yu} \quad (3)$$

where K_{vm} is the stress concentration factor in the polymer as calculated by the Huang-Kinloch model. μ_m is again the pressure sensitivity coefficient and r_{yu} is the classical Irwin prediction of the radius of the damage zone under plane-strain conditions.

The contribution of plastic void growth as a toughening mechanism is given by:

$$\Delta G_v = \left(1 - \frac{\mu_m^2}{3}\right) (V_v - V_p) \sigma_y r_y K_{vm}^2 \quad (4)$$

Where V_v is the volume fraction of voids and the other terms are as previously described.

Both the energy contribution from shear-band yielding, ΔG_s , and the energy contribution from plastic void growth, ΔG_v , are dependent on the pressure sensitivity coefficient, μ_m . The pressure sensitivity coefficient provides a quantitative measure of a polymer's propensity to yield

under various multi-axial stress states. We have demonstrated earlier that the pressure sensitivity coefficient appears to reduce as the epoxy polymers age. Physical aging is related to a reduction in free volume and we suggest here that physical aging is also responsible for the observed reduction in the pressure sensitivity of the epoxy polymers as well. Figure 4 plots the measured fracture energies versus the calculated values of μ_m . The predictions of the Huang-Kinloch model for each volume fraction and varying μ_m have also been plotted as dashed lines. All of the required properties required for the Huang-Kinloch model have been measured directly in the current work with the exception of γ_f , which was assumed to have a value of 0.75. This value is consistent with other previous work on these epoxy systems [5]. A remarkable correlation can be observed especially at high CSR particle loading between the model predictions and the aged fracture energy results. Furthermore, as the aging increases, the fracture energy recorded for the 3 wt.% polymers begins to approach the Huang-Kinloch model predictions. The underprediction of the Huang-Kinloch model for the 3 wt.% samples is of some concern, but has been reported previously for this model system [13]. Future work will concentrate on understanding why this is the case for this system and not for others.

The physical significance and the molecular origins of the pressure dependency coefficient are still not well understood. It is also unclear whether the value of μ_m must be positive, although experimental data in the literature suggests that it always is for a monolithic material, although some lattice structures could have a negative value of μ_m . Thus, we can expect a value of $\mu_m = 0$ to be a limiting case. Note that when $\mu_m = 0$, we will recover the standard von Mises yield criterion and expect that $\sigma_{y,ut} = \sigma_{y,uc}$. The predicted toughness for $\mu_m = 0$ might then represent a lower bound of toughness over the lifetime of the component, or the toughness of the epoxy polymer at $t = \infty$. From the model system studied here, it is clear that this limiting value can be less than half the 'as-manufactured' fracture toughness. This has significant commercial and safety implications for the design of structural components intended for a long life in-service.

Figure 4: Measured fracture energy as function of measured

pressure sensitivity coefficient. The dashed lines reference Huang-Kinloch model predictions.

Conclusions

We have demonstrated, for the first time, that physical aging of epoxy polymers toughened with rubber particles has a negative effect on the toughness of the epoxy polymer. This has important implications for the design of both adhesive joints and composite components using toughened epoxy resins. We have proposed, by resorting to the model outlined by Huang and Kinloch, that this reduction in toughness is linked to a loss in dependency of yield on the hydrostatic stress component as the polymer ages. This further implies that there may exist a lower limit beyond which the polymer will not lose further toughness. We term this the terminal or end-of-life fracture energy and suggest that it is an important material parameter to consider when designing components that will be in-service for a long period of time.

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